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STUDY ON THE PATH OF MODERNISATION OF GOVERNMENT SERVICES--TAKING SICHUAN PROVINCE AS AN EXAMPLE

***Abstract:** This paper takes Sichuan Province as an example to explore the realisation path of government service modernisation. By analysing Sichuan's practices in the areas of 'Internet+Government Services', data sharing and collaborative governance, standardisation and normative construction, and public participation, it summarises its achievements and shortcomings, and proposes a path to optimisation. The study finds that Sichuan province has made significant progress in the digital transformation of government services, but there are still problems such as insufficient data sharing and unbalanced regional development. Finally, the paper puts forward specific suggestions for promoting the modernisation of government services from four dimensions: technology, system, talent and culture.*

***Keywords:** Modernisation of government services; Internet+government services; digital governance; Sichuan Province; path study*

With the rapid development of information technology and the in-depth promotion of national governance modernisation, the modernisation of government services has become an important way to enhance the effectiveness of government governance and optimise the business environment. As a large province in western China, Sichuan Province has actively explored the modernisation of government services in recent years and achieved certain results, but it also faces many challenges. The purpose of this paper is to systematically analyse the current situation and problems of government service modernization in Sichuan Province, and put forward targeted optimization paths, so as to provide reference for the modernisation of government services in the western region and even in China.

I. Theoretical basis for the modernisation of government services

The modernisation of government services refers to the process of reconstructing government service processes, innovating service methods and enhancing service effectiveness through the use of information technology means under the guidance of modern governance concepts. Its core features include: people-centred service concept, data-driven decision-making mechanism, intelligent and efficient service processes, and open and collaborative governance model.

Relevant studies at home and abroad mainly focus on the following aspects: first, the study of the 'Internet + government service' model, such as the study of

Kaifeng City by Sai Jiading et al. (2025); second, the path of digital governance capacity building, such as the study of Han Tong (2022); and third, the relationship between government service and the modernisation of governmental governance, such as the discussion of Wang Qiuju et al. (2019). These studies provide important references for this paper.

II. Analysis of the practice of modernisation of government services in Sichuan Province

2.1 Construction of the 'Internet + Government Services' platform

Sichuan Province has built a government service platform covering the provincial, municipal and county levels, making more than 90 per cent of government service matters available online. For example, the 'Tianfu Citizen Cloud' platform in Chengdu City has integrated more than 200 services and has more than 10 million users. However, there are still obstacles to interconnectivity between platforms, and some functions are duplicated.

2.2 Data sharing and collaborative governance

Sichuan Province has established a platform for sharing and exchanging data on government affairs, with more than 5 billion pieces of data pooled. In epidemic prevention and control, cross-departmental data sharing has been achieved through applications such as health codes. However, data barriers still exist, and the efficiency of inter-departmental collaboration needs to be improved. Data sharing and collaborative governance

2.3 Standardisation and Normalisation

Sichuan Province has formulated a standardised list of administrative service matters and promoted the 'one-window acceptance' and 'one-run-at-largest' reforms. However, in grass-roots implementation, the phenomenon of standards not being put into place has occurred from time to time.

III. Optimising the Path to Modernising Government Services in Sichuan Province

3.1 Technology path

3.1.1 Improving digital infrastructure: promoting the application of new technologies such as 5G and the Internet of Things, and upgrading network coverage in remote areas.

3.1.2 Strengthen platform integration: build a unified government service platform across the province and eliminate information silos.

3.1.3 Strengthen data governance: establish a perfect data quality management system and enhance data value.

3.2 Institutional path

3.2.1 Sound regulations and standards: formulate the Regulations on Government Services of Sichuan Province and improve the standard system.

3.2.2 Optimise the organisational structure: set up a provincial digital government construction leading group to strengthen coordination.

3.2.3 Innovative assessment mechanism: incorporate data sharing and business collaboration into government performance assessment.

IV. Conclusion

The modernisation of government services in Sichuan Province has achieved stage-by-stage results, but still faces many challenges. In the future, it should adhere to systematic thinking, promote the construction of technology and system in an integrated manner, and create a government service modernisation model with western characteristics. With the in-depth development of digital technology and continuous innovation of governance concepts, the level of modernisation of government services in Sichuan Province will continue to improve, providing strong support for the high-quality development of western China.

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